

Cognitive-Behaviourism, Constructivism and Humanism in Paediatrics Specialty Training: From theory to practice

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ABSTRACT The study of human learning is constantly changing and developing facilitated by using learning theories like cognitive-behaviourism, constructivism and humanism, which are the primary guide for both academic and clinical training, including paediatrics. Current advances in medical education in postgraduate medical training suggests that trainees, educational and clinical supervisors can hugely benefit from a robust understanding of learning theory and its right application in clinical practice in outpatient clinics, inpatient ward rounds, clinical skills teaching and multidisciplinary meetings. Consultants and senior medical staff involved in teaching and training of postgraduate doctors in paediatrics can review these theories and their approaches to targeted learning goals to increase the skill set to cope with present demand and to produce sound and skilled paediatricians. This narrative review aims to provide paediatricians clinical and educational supervisors opportunities to be theoretically grounded in the dynamics of selected learning theories leveraging on their right application to achieve the learning goals of paediatric speciality training and inform excellent medical scholarship. The combination of these theories in the raising next generation of paediatricians is a viable pathway in postgraduate medical training.

KEYWORDS Learning theory, learning, paediatrics, medical education

Introduction

In history, traditional learning theories have been regarded as applicable only to early learning and, thus described as not relevant to the educational needs of adults [1]. Currently learning and teaching theories are regarded as complex, comprehensive frameworks of principles, ideas and concepts that acknowledge the existence of different types of learning, and the influence of the social context within which it occurs [2]. This gives a foundation for effective and efficient teaching methods in the dissemination of relevant information, meeting both the needs of the learner and curriculum [2].

Learning theories are a set of organized principles on how individuals develop and learn and ultimately progress. Schunk [3] submits that learning involves acquiring and modifying knowledge, skills, strategies, beliefs, attitudes, and behaviours. People learn cognitive, linguistic, motor and social skills, and these can take many forms. Theories provide frameworks for interpreting environmental observations and serve as bridges between research and education [4]. Behavioural and cognitive theories are the two main theories of learning, which both historical and modern-day approaches are based upon.

Training paediatrics in the UK is made up of 5-8 years of training on three levels [5] as shown in fig 1, level 1 and 2 training include general paediatrics, neonatology and community paediatrics while level 3 involves sub specialisation, or trainees can choose to continue in general paediatrics delivered in a tertiary and accredited hospitals to achieve standard competencies. One of the key components of effective learning in paediatrics training is an appropriate application of learning theories in paediatrics, including trainees and tutors attitudes, sociocultural and emotional factors and appropriate learning environment [6].

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Figure 1: Training framework in paediatrics.

Appropriate environment suitable for effective communication to discuss and learn from mistakes and also for an adequate mentoring relationship [7].

This review gives an overview of the concepts behind learning theories and their implications to paediatrics training including necessary skills on the part of supervisor, teachers and preceptors, to apply these theories in the clinical teaching environment. Also appraising these theories and will discuss how theory is translated into practice.

Discussion

Three prominent concepts surrounding these sterling theories will be explored including, cognitive-behaviourism (Bandura), constructivism (Lave & Wenger) and Humanism (Maslow), see table 1.

Behavioural learning theories focus on how behaviours are gained. Behaviourist theories accept the idea that learning takes place by establishing a connection between the stimulant and the behaviour and that changing behaviour is possible through reinforcement [8]. Behaviourists handle learning as a mechanical process and give priority to objectivity. The experiences and environment shape a person's personality, and the behavioural theories stress the role of the environment, specifically, with regards to how stimuli are arranged and presented and how responses are reinforced.

Cognitive theories describe the role of learners' thoughts, beliefs, attitudes, and values. Cognitive theories focus on attention, perception, memory, forgetting and retrieval [9]. Cognitive theories acknowledge the role of environmental conditions as influences on learning. Teachers' explanations and demonstrations of concepts serve as environmental inputs for students.

Cognitive-Behavioural theory

Albert Bandura [10] proposed the social learning theory in 1977; this theory builds on the behaviourist theories of classical and operant conditioning, describing how stimuli trigger a response through mediating processes. Although the theory acknowledges that learning occurs as a result of interaction with others and the environment, Bandura believed that cognitive processes were necessary for observational learning to occur [11]. This theory has been labelled a bridge between behaviourist and cognitive learning theories. There are four steps in observational learning involves four steps including attention that is required for learning; Information that stored for later retrieval (retention); retained information for the performance of observed behaviour (reproduction) and motivation required to imitate learnt behaviour. This via reinforcement – either direct reinforcement, vicarious reinforcement or self-reinforcement.

Bandura's theory suggests that we learn from observing our

environment. In Paediatrics, learners initially observe their trainer or clinical supervisor in ward rounds, clinical outpatient's neonatal intensive care units, observing communication and negotiation skills and how they use their space to conduct successful consultations, result-oriented ward- rounds and family discussion in hospital. Furthermore, trainee doctors in paediatrics observe consultants and other senior clinical staff performing procedures, conducting clinics and communicating with patients and their families. An essential aspect of this role is the demonstration of good clinical practice, confidence, enthusiasm and a positive attitude to patient and learner. Morris & Neve [12] states that observing positive role models help to shape the development of learner's professionalism. In paediatrics training, Bandura's learning theory is widely applicable in roles such as observation, deputising and fellowships.

There is an active dynamic learning process ongoing between the clinical supervisor and trainee. A clinical supervisor's role is to provide and optimise a conducive learning environment that is for trainees for maximum attention, keen observation and imitation of the teacher or model effect.

Learning from role-models is commonly used in the medical educational method during clinical rotations [13]. Wright & Carrese [14] describe the attributes of a successful doctor role-model as having good and sound clinical knowledge, competent skills and a patient-centred approach with a display of empathy and compassion, this is crucial in paediatrics when dealing with children and their families. An impact-making clinical supervisor can be either a 'live model' where they demonstrate sterling and positive behaviour, a 'verbal instructional model' which entails describing a behaviour to learners, or provide a 'symbolic model' with the ultimate of reproducing sound paediatricians to gloriously impact the healthcare system, community and the global academic community at large.

Communities of Practice Learning Theory

This theory entails learning by observation from fellow trainees or clinical staffs and furthermore becoming a part of the working and learning community, acquiring a shared knowledge and practice involving attendance at educational and multidisciplinary meetings. These are often followed by lunch and a more informal discussion about the practice, patients, staff and politics. All these situations create a great learning opportunity at a community level. Communities of Practice (CoP) are groups of people who share a concern or passion for something they do and learn how to improve as they regularly interact [15]. Three significant characteristics of a community are domain, community and practice. Communities develop their practice through varying methods, which include problem-solving, reflection, mapping knowledge, and identifying gaps [16]. Wegner [17] posits that learning is central to human identity, whereby social participation is the primary focus.

In paediatrics training community of practice can be demonstrated through both formal and informal collaborative learning. Formal methods include the get-together of paediatrics trainees (junior and senior registrars), medical or nursing students, nurses consultants and other allied clinical staffs weekly multidisciplinary or teaching sessions were difficult or interesting cases are presented and discussed for improvement of knowledge and skills. Continuous medical education sessions with other specialities is also a community of practice model.

Informal demonstration of a community of practice involves when paediatrics trainees casually or subconsciously share their clinical experiences over coffee or lunch and learn from each

Table 1 Summary of Learning Theories.

Learning Theory	Cognitive-Behaviourism	Constructivism	Humanism
Brief Definition	Learners acquire cognitive representation from role-modelling, behavioural rehearsal and observed behaviour to assume new roles.	An active process; new facts are accommodated and assimilated with pre-existing facts, ideas and experience to form knowledge.	The self-directed learning process to unlock the learner's full potential.
Key Concepts	Learning results from the interaction with and the observation of others in a social context.	Learning is the construction of new and pre-existing knowledge.	Autonomous, self-directed. Auto-evaluation and criticism.
Associated Theories	Bandura's Social Learning Theory	Vygotsky's Social Development Theory Communities of Practice	Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs
Influential Theorists	Bandura (1986)	Vygotsky (1980) Lave & Wenger (1991)	Maslow (1943)

other's experiences between junior trainees and their consultants.

The role of a teacher or consultants in the informal setting of a community of practice model is minimal as it mainly involves a group of paediatrics trainees (community) with a similar passion (the domain), sharing cases, stories, and experience from their practice [18]. In the formal setting, teachers play an essential role and require skills to ensure adequate facilitation with good communication skill, active listening, and rapport building to encourage effective communication in the team. Furthermore, facilitation involves the ability to structure, organise effectively, and summarise ideas and learning points gathered from the discussion [18]. The community of practice is deeply interactive and contextual in learning through maximum co-participation within a social and physical environment with learning occurring from different perspectives through engagement leading to the rapid transmission of information among participants. Members can have different functional responsibilities but share a mutual product accountability [19, 20]. The community of practice emphasises the importance of integrating individuals within a professional community, such as the medical team within a department. This social network of individuals sharing an overlapping knowledge base allows for knowledge translation [15].

Humanist Learning Theory

Humanism is a philosophy entrenched in the belief that learning is an act to the fulfilment of one's potential through self or

personal development transcending intellectual development to educating the whole man including interest, goal, motivation and enthusiasm [21]. This approach is student-centred and transfers the responsibility for learning from the teacher to the learner. This may be in the form of self-directed learning where outcomes are met, but the learner decides how and when to meet those outcomes. This model naturally encourages a reflective approach and helps to prepare the learner for independent learning in the future. An example of this in medical education is student self-selected topics for coursework or reflective practice logs while students are on clinical placements. Humanism theory is related to one's growth and explores one's own emotions and changing identity. It is essentially a self-directed approach that allows the learner to become self-directed and autonomous in the process of learning. In this theory, the paediatrician trainer and trainee relationship are based on mutual respect and the trainer who has had self-discovery should be emotionally ready to honestly share his or her feelings and experience with the trainees comfortably and also value trainees feelings and desires.

Conclusion

Training in paediatrics constantly face the challenge in delivering a full training package amid constant changes and complexity of the medical field. This report has considered the significance of educational theory in medical training, highlighting the im-

portance of hands-on practice, socialisation and communication. Utilising educational theories and derived principles as a basis in teaching, will inevitably augment learners' knowledge, skills, and positive attitudes. Applied learning theories and experiences will produce better-trained doctors who deliver enhanced patient care with improved patient outcomes.

Competing Interests

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest in this study.

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